

PROBE WG2 “Advanced ABL profiling” - Deliverable 2.1

Forecast indices

D2.1: Reports, white and review papers on key ABL parameters, their applications, and the end-user requirements.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This section focuses on Forecast Indices retrievals from existing and future observations, presenting an overview of the product capabilities (accuracy, uncertainty estimates, readiness for operation etc...). Existing processing chains are also reported and published references are listed so that the reader can get more details on specific aspects if necessary.

Through all the documents the following acronyms are used:

- MWR: MicroWave Radiometer (20 to 60 GHz spectral bands)
- NN: Neural Network
- wv-DIAL: water vapor Differential Absorption Lidar (wavelength depending on the DIAL system)
- ABL: Atmospheric Boundary Layer
- Hyperspectral infrared sensors:
 - Ground-based: e.g., Atmospheric Emitted Radiance Interferometer (AERI, 520-3300 cm^{-1})
 - Space-borne: e.g., InfraRed Sounder on board the Meteosat Third Generation Sounder (MTG-IRS, 700 to 1210 cm^{-1} and 1600 to 2175 cm^{-1}).

2 METHODS OVERVIEW

Forecast indices (FI) have been developed since more than 60 years ago (REF) to relate atmospheric profiles measured by radiosondes to potential for high impact weather such as thunderstorm, fog, wind gusts. Several FI have been proposed in the past most of which are based on similar thermodynamic approaches. The FI considered here include K index, total totals (TT), KO index, lifted index (LI), S index (SI), fog threat (FT), and convective available potential energy (CAPE). Although FI based on sounding observations are rather simple, they perform reasonably well, especially once optimized for site-specific conditions, and show forecast skills comparable with those of numerical weather prediction models. As such, FI are still broadly used in operational meteorology and local short-term forecast.

Temperature and humidity profiles retrieved from ground-based instruments (e.g., MWR, AERI) can be used to feed tools developed for processing radiosonde observations to obtain FI commonly used in operational meteorology. FI computed from ground-based remote sensing retrieved temperature and humidity profiles have been compared to those obtained from radiosondes, taken as a reference, showing different performances depending upon index and environmental situation. Overall, FIs computed from ground-based remote sensing retrievals agree well with radiosonde values, with correlation coefficients usually above 0.8, with the advantage (with respect to radiosondes) of nearly continuous updates (Cimini et al., 2015).

Statistical retrieval methods such as Neural Networks (NN) can be used to calculate FI directly from satellite- and ground-based observations as well as from their synergy. Satellite observations from geostationary platforms offer the possibility to monitor FI with high temporal (15-30min) and horizontal (6 km for MSG-SEVIRI and 7-8km for the future MTG-IRS) resolution (Koenig and de Coning (2009), EUMETSAT 2021). However, these observations are performed in the infrared part of the spectra and have limitations such as cloudiness, uncertain information on surface emissivity and low accuracy and resolution in the boundary layer (Pougatchev et al., 2009). These limitations can be reduced by constraining satellite observations with ground-based remote sensing.

Theoretical studies have been performed to assess the potential of ground-based MWR and DIAL to complement the future geostationary, hyperspectral InfraRed Sounder (IRS) on board the Meteosat Third Generation Sounder Satellite (MTG-S), and to provide information on atmospheric stability. The experiments were performed for single instruments and their synergy. First study shows the potential of single ground-based sensors in synergy with satellite observations. The second, the potential of a network of ground-based MWR to complement future hyperspectral IRS observations. Both studies were performed using the COSMO-REA2 reanalysis.

The first study (Toporov, Löhnert 2020) is based on the COSMO-REA2 output at the Jülich Observatory for Cloud Evolution (JOYCE) in Germany, which is located at 50°30' N, 6°48' E at 111 m above sea level. The atmospheric profiles for the time period from May to September from 2007–13 were selected. According to the total amount of ice and water in each profile the whole profile set was divided into clear-sky (9430 profiles) and cloudy (14 294 profiles). Both datasets were used for the simulation of ground-

based (MWR, DIAL) and satellite remote sensing observations (SEVIRI, IRS, IASI, AMSU-A) and for the calculation of FI. Here, we show the results for the future IRS since it will provide observations with highest temporal, spatial and spectral resolution.

The simulated observations were used to train, validate and test Neural Network (NN) retrievals of seven FI. Each index has an empirically determined threshold. In case the index exceeds or falls below this threshold, the potential for convection, thunder storm, or fog, depending on the index, is given. Then, taking into account the threshold values of FI, the performance of the retrieval can be verified by calculating the number of correct and wrong forecasted events and non-events. On the basis of these four outcomes different verification parameters can be derived. Here we show three of them, the probability of detection (POD), the false alarm ratio (FAR), and the Heidke skill score (HSS). The higher the values of POD and HSS, and the lower the value of FAR, the more accurate the retrieval of FI. Figure 1 shows the statistics for retrievals based on observations of MWR and IRS (non-transparent part of the bars) with transparent extension corresponding to the improvements due to additional ground-based observations (IRS+MWR, IRS+DIAL and IRS+MWR+DIAL).

Figure 1: Probability of Detection (POD), False Alarm Ratio (FAR) and Heidke Skill Score (HSS) for seven FI retrieved from simulated observations of ground-based MWR, satellite-based IRS and from IRS observations combined with ground-based sensors (MWR, DIAL). The non-transparent part of the bars shows the single instrument score, whereas transparent extension corresponds to improvements due to synergy with ground-based observations. Note that FAR for synergistic retrieval is lower than for single IRS and is shown by horizontal black dash. Upper and lower rows show the statistics for clear sky and cloudy dataset, respectively.

For the **clear sky** dataset, the MWR provides the values of POD, FAR, and HSS comparable to those achieved by IRS for three of the FI: KI, KO, and LI (non-transparent part of the bars). For TT and SI, the lower values of POD and higher number of false alarms retrieved by MWR result in lower HSS relative to IRS retrieval. More accurate retrievals are provided by MWR for two indices: CAPE and FT. Both indices are strongly dependent on temperature and humidity in the lowest atmospheric layer close to the surface, where the accuracy of satellite observations degrades.

The benefit of combining the satellite with ground-based observations (transparent part of the bar) can be seen for all FI. The contribution of single ground-based sensors MWR and DIAL is comparable and leads to similar values of HSS for all FI with exception of FT, which benefits most from additional humidity observations from DIAL. In the case of FT, the combination IRS+MWR achieves POD, FAR and HSS values similar to those of MWR retrieval. These results show that for the assessment of potential for radiation fog, the broadband and hyperspectral infrared satellite observations cannot add complementary information in a synergistic retrieval and thus can neither replace nor complement the ground-based observation, even under clear-sky conditions. The best results for the first five indices are provided by the combination IRS+MWR+DIAL, with the HSS lying around 0.8 and corresponding POD

in the range between 0.8 and 0.87 under clear-sky conditions. The false alarms appear in 10%–15% of predicted cases. The retrieval of CAPE and FT is less accurate even with a synergistic approach IRS+MWR+DIAL, with FAR around 0.4 and POD and HSS values lower than for the other five FI.

The POD, FAR, and HSS values calculated for **cloudy** cases clearly illustrate the advantage of ground-based MWR and DIAL observations in the presence of clouds. The POD, FAR, and HSS values for ground-based MWR remain almost the same as for clear-sky conditions, whereas the POD and HSS for IRS decrease for all FI. The synergistic retrieval IRS+MWR shows better results than IRS+DIAL, since in the presence of clouds, the DIAL provides humidity profiles only up to the cloud base. The synergistic retrieval IRS+MWR+DIAL leads to the highest POD (between 0.78 and 0.9) and HSS (between 0.68 and 0.91) for five indices. For KI and TT, the statistics for IRS+MWR are similar to that for IRS+MWR+DIAL.

The second study shows the potential of complementing the future IRS with a network of ground-based MWR to provide information on atmospheric stability. Here, we consider a hypothetical MWR network over the western part of Germany to deliver the missing thermodynamic ABL information which the satellite cannot access. Based on the COSMO-REA2 reanalysis as "truth", a neural network retrieval of CAPE and LI from simulated IRS, MWR and combined IRS+MWR measurements was developed. Considering a single atmospheric column and clear sky conditions, both instruments, MWR and IRS, achieve almost similar accuracy with correlation values of 0.79 and 0.92 for CAPE and LI, respectively. Under cloudy conditions, MWR shows similar performance as under clear sky conditions, whereas the accuracy of IRS retrievals degrades leading to correlation values of 0.68 for CAPE and 0.79 for LI. The synergistic approach (i.e., using combined observations MWR+IRS as the input for neural networks) is beneficial under both, clear sky and cloudy conditions. The MWR+IRS retrieval is less sensitive to the presence of clouds and results in the correlation values of 0.88 and 0.97 for CAPE and LI, respectively.

To assess the spatial representativeness of observations of a single ground-based MWR and to investigate the impact of the MWR network in the presence of horizontally resolved IRS observations, the derived retrievals were applied to MWR and IRS observations simulated over the 150*150 km² reanalysis domain covering the Rhein-Ruhr area. Using spatial statistical interpolation, the fields of CAPE/LI retrieved from IRS observations were merged with the CAPE/LI values from a network of MWR. The number of MWR distributed in the domain varied from 1 to 200. In the grid points with MWR, the synergistic retrieval (MWR+IRS) was applied to show the maximal possible impact. Within the statistical interpolation, the weight given to the CAPE/LI values in the grid points with available MWR observation is determined by the relationship between the error variance of both retrievals, IRS and MWR+IRS. The impact of MWR observations in the surrounding grid points is mostly determined by the error covariance matrix of IRS retrieval.

The left plots in Fig. 2 a) and b) show the root mean squared error (RMSE) of the CAPE and LI fields retrieved from IRS observations. The interpolation between the IRS retrieved fields and CAPE/LI values from a single MWR decreases the uncertainty of obtained CAPE/LI fields in and around the location of MWR (middle plot). For a network of 10 MWR (assumed to measure in the grid points with current SYNOP stations of DWD) the relative improvement in terms of RMSE compared to IRS retrieved fields lies by 10% and 25% for CAPE and LI respectively. The above results are shown for an all-sky data set. Considering the clear sky and cloudy cases separately, the decrease of the error and thus, the impact of additional ground-based MWR observations is more pronounced under cloudy conditions.

Figure 2: a) RMSE of CAPE retrievals; b) RMSE of LI retrievals; RMSE fields are shown for 150*150 km² domain in western Germany. The left plots of each figure group show the RMSE values when only satellite observations are used as input, the middle plots using one additional ground-based MWR in the domain center, the right plots using 10 additional MWRs (corresponding to current SYNOP stations deployed by DWD) to complement the satellite retrieval. The number in the right lower corner gives the averaged RMSE value for the shown domain.

Figure 3: Dependency of RMSE of the CAPE (left) and LI (right) analysis (entire data set separated into clear sky and cloudy cases) on the number of MWR distributed in the domain. The blue dots indicate the statistics for the IRS retrieved CAPE/LI values. Red lines correspond to the analysis based on interpolation of IRS retrieved fields and MWR-network values of CAPE/LI obtained using synergistic MWR+IRS retrieval.

Figure 3 shows the RMSE values calculated for the entire domain for the network with up to 200 MWR for clear sky and cloudy conditions separately (solid and dashed lines). 200 microwave radiometers hardly state a technically feasible scenario, however in this way the value of adding instruments can be quantified.

For CAPE, the RMSE decreases steadily with the growing number of MWR, while HSS (not shown), which gives the efficiency of event /non-event forecast, improves strongly (especially for cloudy conditions) for the first one to 25 MWR (corresponds to ~40 km distance between the instruments) and reaches saturation when more sensors are included. For LI, the levelling off of the RMSE decrease can be seen already at a smaller number of MWR (10-15) compared to CAPE. Under cloudy conditions, even one MWR in the center of the domain leads to a reduction of RMSE by 6% and 13% for CAPE and LI, respectively.

3 PRODUCTS OVERVIEW

Four types of algorithms exist:

Product 1 and 2:

FI based on temperature and humidity profiles retrieved from ground-based MWR observations (Cimini et al., 2015) and AERI (Blumberg et al., 2017).

Product 3:

Neural network retrieval of FI from following observations (Toporov and Löhnert, 2020; Toporov, 2021):

- ground-based MWR
- satellite IRS
- combined satellite and ground-based observations (i.e., IRS+MWR, IRS+MWR+DIAL, IRS+DIAL)

Product 4:

Fields of CAPE and LI obtained through interpolation of CAPE/LI fields obtained from space-borne IRS measurements (using the NN-retrieval from 2) with CAPE/LI values from a network of ground-based MWR (Toporov, 2021).

	Forecast indices
Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MWR - AERI - IRS - IRS + MWR - IRS + DIAL

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IRS + MWR + DIAL
Accuracy requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requirements not yet defined - Expected accuracy (inferred from field data): ~0.8 correlation with respect to reference radiosonde
Temporal resolution Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Order of minutes to an hour
Applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weather alerts - Air quality alerts
End-Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Weather Services - Air quality agency
Existing algorithms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forecast indices can be derived from temperature and humidity profiles previously retrieved ⁴ (as also provided by manufacturers). - Product 1 and 2: for MWR or AERI: TROPoe and SHARPPy ^{2,3} (physically-based retrievals). Input: brightness temperatures as measured by MWR or AERI. Output: FI for considered location. - Product 3: for MWR and synergistic IRS+MWR, IRS+MWR+DIAL, IRS+DIAL: Neural network or statistical regressions applied to the raw measurements ^{5,6}. Input: brightness temperatures as measured by MWR, IRS and water vapor profiles from DIAL. Output: FI for considered location. - Product 4: Interpolation of IRS retrieved CAPE/LI fields and CAPE/LI values from a network of MWR with varying number of sensors⁶. Input: FI from IRS and MWR network observations calculated using product 3. Output: Fields of FI.
Assumptions needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For MWR and AERI: Clear and cloudy (non-precipitating) conditions - For IRS: Clear and cloudy conditions. In cloudy conditions, depending on the cloud water content, reduced accuracy of retrievals.
Accuracy of existing products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluation of derived forecast indices can be found here: from MWR derived profiles⁴, from AERI derived profiles³, neural network retrievals from MWR, IRS, IRS+MWR+DIAL ^{5,6}. - The accuracy of NN retrievals depends on the forecast index and on the sensor. For single satellite IRS, correlations above 0.7 for CAPE and FT and above 0.8 for other FI were shown under clear sky conditions. Under cloudy conditions correlations for most of the FI are below 0.7. Single MWR observations provide correlations above 0.7 for CAPE and above 0.8 for other FI under all sky. Synergistic approaches IRS+MWR, IRS+DIAL and IRS+MWR+DIAL lead to correlations above 0.8 for CAPE and LI and above 0.9 for other FI under both, clear and cloudy conditions.
Uncertainty estimates existing?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product 2: yes - Products 1,3,4: no

Readiness for operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product 1 and 2: Yes, FI based on atm. profiles from MWR, AERI, DIAL using TROPoe+SHARPPy. - Product 3: NN for MWR and DIAL: further evaluation of the products with real observations is necessary, but instrumentation is operational. - Product 3: NN for IRS and satellite+ground-based synergy: a larger evaluation is needed. Real observations not yet available. - Product 4: Interpolated CAPE/LI fields from IRS and MWR-network: application possible only for considered domain. Further testing on different domains and with real observations is required.
Temporal resolution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MWR (depends on scanning strategy): 2 to 5 min averaging time typically every 20 minutes - AERI: 20-30s - DIAL: 1 min reporting time resolution, 20 min averaging time - IRS: 30 min over Europe
Timeliness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - < 5 minutes for MWR and DIAL. AERI: 20-30s - ~20-30 minutes for IRS (depending on the timeliness of IRS. Expected timeliness ~15 min. for level-1 spectra).
Data availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MWR: 24/7 in non-precipitation conditions. - AERI: 24/7 in non-precipitation conditions. - IRS: 24/7 (with varying information content for clear sky and cloudy scenes).
Data format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For MWR, IRS and DIAL: netCDF.

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